

NUMERICAL STUDY ON THE INFLUENCE OF TYLER-SOFRIN MODES ON EXCITATION
FORCES IN 1.5-STAGE AXIAL COMPRESSORS

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ABSTRACT

Rotor-stator interaction in axial compressors generates Tyler-Sofrin modes (T-S modes). T-S modes generated on each stage propagate through a compressor, and change the excitation forces at different stages, so-called multi-stage interference. The propagation characteristics of T-S modes are determined by the blade count difference between rotors and stators. At the same time, the difference of blade counts changes amplitude of the T-S modes. In present paper, the relationship between the combination of blade counts and excitation forces was numerically investigated. The investigation was performed on a quasi-three-dimensional 1.5-stage compressor model comprising rotor-stator-rotor configurations. By independently varying the blade counts of the two rotors, the circumferential wavenumber of T-S modes occurring within the compressor was controlled. The excitation force acting on the blades was found to vary significantly depending on the combination of blade and vane counts in each stage. Modal forces acting on the blades were decomposed by nodal diameter to identify and analyze the excitation sources. Amplitude of T-S modes were also evaluated to understand how T-S modes from another stage affect the change in excitation forces. As a result, it was found that T-S modes from adjacent stage changed the excitation force of nodal diameter estimated by the difference of blade counts between rotor and stator; not only modal forces corresponding to T-S modes from adjacent stage. Furthermore, it was also found that T-S modes can reach adjacent stages and influence their excitation forces, even when they are acoustically cut-off condition. Although this phenomenon requires further investigation, the results suggest that in axial compressor design, unexpected high responses can potentially be reduced by selecting blade counts such that the amplitude of T-S modes is low.

Keywords: Forced Response, Unsteady Aerodynamics, URANS-Method, Numerical Study

NOMENCLATURE

B_i	blade count of i-th rotor blade
c	speed of sound
C	chord length of the rotor blade
f	modal force
f_{norm}	normalized modal force
k_1	index related to T-S mode circumferential wavenumber for 1SV
k_t	circumferential angular wavenumber of a T-S mode
m	circumferential wavenumber of a T-S mode
n_i	index related to T-S mode circumferential wavenumber for i-th rotor blade
M	absolute Mach number
M_t	circumferential Mach number
M_x	axial Mach number
R	radius
SF	scale factor
V_1	vane count of 1SV
Ω	rotor speed
ω_i	angular frequency of i-th harmonic of blade passing frequency

1. INTRODUCTION

Flight safety is one of the most important concerns in the design of aircraft gas turbines engines. In axial compressors for gas turbines, excessive blade vibration can lead to blade failure due to high-cycle fatigue. Therefore, vibratory stress caused by blade vibration must be reduced to prevent such failures. However, modern blades of axial compressors have become thinner to meet aerodynamic design and weight requirements for reducing fuel consumption. This trend makes aeromechanical design even more difficult. Therefore, more advanced forced response prediction methods are required to achieve aerodynamic performance while satisfying aeromechanical criteria.

To accurately predict vibratory stress due to forced blade vibration, it is essential to understand the mechanism of excitation force generation. In forced blade vibration, the excitation force is generated by the vortical wake or potential field of the relatively moving adjacent blade rows. Therefore, it has been presumed that the excitation force can be reasonably estimated from steady-state aerodynamic characteristics, such as the strength of the excitation source—i.e., the wake and potential of the blade row. However, some previous studies have indicated that the excitation force depends not only on steady-state aerodynamic characteristics, but also on the blade counts of the rotor blades and stator vanes.

Li and Kielb compared unsteady aerodynamic forces and excitation forces for different blade count ratios between stator vanes and rotor blades, while keeping the steady-state aerodynamic characteristics constant [1]. They found that the unsteady aerodynamic force varied with the blade count ratio. Similarly, Chen et al. investigated the relationship between blade count ratio and harmonic aerodynamic forces in a steam turbine, reporting a steep increase in unsteady forces at a specific blade count ratio [2]. Fruth et al. also studied the relationship between blade count ratio and excitation forces, reporting that the variation in force with blade count ratio depended on the vibration mode of the blade [3].

The authors have also conducted several studies on the relationship between blade count ratio and aerodynamic excitation. Numerical investigations of a low-speed axial compressor with various blade count ratios were performed [4-6]. As a result, it was found that the pressure amplitude on the blade surface due to rotor-stator interaction increases at a specific blade count ratio. This increase was initially considered to be due to acoustic resonance between blade rows. However, it was later indicated that the condition for this increase was independent of physical scale, i.e., the axial gap between blade rows. Finally, it was found that this increase was dominated by the modal phase velocity of a Tyler-Sofrin mode [5, 6], which is generated by stator-rotor interaction. Tyler-Sofrin modes are acoustic modes spinning in the circumferential direction, and their modal phase velocity depends on the mode number [7]. Here, the mode number is determined by the blade counts of the stator and rotor; therefore, the mode number depends on the blade count ratio, resulting in the modal phase velocity also depending on the blade count ratio. In these studies [4-6], it was found that the pressure amplitude increases when the modal phase velocity approaches the circumferential velocity of acoustic propagation. The phase speed ratio—the ratio of the two velocities—was introduced to explain their relationship. It was shown that the pressure amplitude increases near 1.0.

Many researchers have conducted studies on the Tyler-Sofrin mode in the field of aeroacoustics; however, recent research has reported the effects of the Tyler-Sofrin mode on forced blade vibration. Schöenenborn et al. showed that Tyler-Sofrin acoustically spinning modes can have a significant impact on blade excitation forces [8, 9]. The Tyler-Sofrin modes may also generate forces of different nodal diameters at a specific excitation frequency for the stage 2 rotor of a 4.5-stage

compressor [10], which was experimentally proven in reference [11]. Pinelli et al. reported that Tyler-Sofrin acoustic interaction may be strong enough to cause measurable levels of structural response [12]. Mårtensson and Billson reported that the excitation force on fan blades due to inlet distortion increases near the cut-off/on boundary, in both 3D [13] and 2D numerical simulations [14].

Regarding the forced response in multi-stage compressors, the characteristics of the T-S mode have at least two distinct effects. The first is a change in excitation force due to the superposition of T-S modes generated in multiple stages. The second is a change in excitation force caused by variations in the amplitude of pressure fluctuations of the T-S mode itself, depending on its propagation characteristics. Both effects are significantly influenced by basic parameters such as the blade counts in the compressor; however, there are few studies investigating the relationship between blade count and excitation force in multi-stage compressors. In this study, the effect of blade count on excitation force in 1.5-stage axial compressors is investigated using simple numerical simulations to analyze the resulting trends.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Models for numerical investigations

The compressor chosen for this study is the "Purdue 3-Stage Axial Compressor (P3S)" [15, 16]. This compressor is a subsonic 3.5-stage compressor designed for experimental use, including inlet guide vanes. The present study focuses on multi-stage interference caused by T-S modes. Therefore, the 1.5-stage, consisting of the 1RB, 1SV, and 2RB rows of this compressor, was selected for analysis. In this configuration, both the 1RB and 2RB experience excitation forces at harmonics of the 1SV passing frequency, but these forces are caused by different T-S modes generated by the interactions between 1RB-1SV and 1SV-2RB. Excitation forces acting on the 1RB and 2RB are investigated in this study. All calculations were performed without considering blade vibratory deformation. To reduce computational cost, the midspan of blade height cross-section of the compressor was extracted, and all simulations were conducted as quasi-3D calculations.

The original blade counts are 36, 38, and 33 for the 1RB, 1SV, and 2RB, respectively. To vary the T-S mode number generated in each stage, the blade counts of the 1RB and 2RB were changed independently, while the blade count of the 1SV was kept constant to maintain the excitation frequency. The generation of T-S modes changes drastically near their cut-on boundary [4-6, 13, 14]. To consider this effect on the excitation forces, the blade counts of the 1RB and 2RB were varied from 16 to 30 and 17 to 31, respectively, while the vane count of the 1SV was fixed at 38. All configurations are summarized in Table 1. The calculations were performed for 25 cases in total, with five different blade counts selected for both 1RB and 2RB. To maintain steady aerodynamic characteristics, the rotor blades of each configuration were scaled according to the scaling factor

SF, which is determined by Eq. (1), so that the solidity of the vane cascade is kept constant.

$$SF = B_{orig}/B \quad (1)$$

The axial gap between the stator and the rotor is kept constant in this study. Blade shapes of the maximum and minimum blade sizes are shown in Figure 1.

2.2 Tyler-Sofrin modes

Interaction between stator and rotor produces pressure perturbations at integer multiples of the blade passing frequency. These perturbations at each frequency have circumferential modes, the wave numbers of these modes are determined by the counts of stator vanes and rotor blades. These circumferential modes are known as Tyler-Sofrin modes. The circumferential mode number m is determined by the rotor blade counts B_1 , B_2 , and the stator vane count V_1 , along with arbitrary integers n_1 , n_2 and k_1 as shown in Eq. (2).

$$m = n_1 B_1 + k_1 V_1 + n_2 B_2 \quad (2)$$

Tyler-Sofrin modes propagate in the duct both upstream and downstream when their modal characteristics satisfy the following inequality [17].

$$\frac{M_t - \sqrt{1 - M_x^2}}{1 - M^2} < \frac{ck_t}{\omega_i} < \frac{M_t + \sqrt{1 - M_x^2}}{1 - M^2} \quad (3)$$

TABLE 1: BLADE AND VANE COUNT CONFIGURATIONS USED IN CALCULATIONS

	Blade / Vane Counts
1RB	16, 20, 24, 28, 30
1SV	38
2RB	17, 21, 25, 29, 31

FIGURE 1: BLADE SHAPES FOR DIFFERENT BLADE COUNT CONFIGURATIONS (EXAMPLES OF MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM ROTOR BLADE SIZES)

Here, k_t denotes the circumferential wave number, and is defined as $k_t = m/R$. ω_1 and ω_2 are the frequencies of the disturbances from 1RB and 2RB, respectively, and are determined by the following equation.

$$\omega_i = n_i B_i \Omega \quad (4)$$

Eq. (3) is used to classify whether acoustic modes are cut-on or cut-off. According to the equation, T-S modes with higher frequency and lower circumferential wave number become cut-on in a similar flow field.

2.3 Numerical settings

In this study, the 3D Navier-Stokes solver UPACS, developed by Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency, is used to obtain the unsteady flow field. UPACS is a multi-block finite volume solver employing an implicit time-marching method. Further details of this solver are described in [18]. In the present calculations, the convective fluxes are computed using a third-order MUSCL scheme, while the viscous fluxes are computed using a second-order central scheme. For turbulence modeling, the Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model is employed.

All numerical simulations are performed using a quasi-3D approach, as previously described. Unsteady flow simulations are conducted using the Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) method, with a full annulus computational domain and the sliding-mesh technique.

The computational domain and grid are shown in Figure 2. The grid consists of 5 points in the spanwise direction and approximately 60,000 points per single passage for each blade row. The inlet and outlet sections are extended to about 10 times the chord length of the rotor blade, and the mesh is stretched to serve as a buffer zone near the inlet and outlet boundaries. Pressure waves in the axial direction are dissipated in these buffer zones, reducing numerical reflection at the inlet and outlet boundaries. To accurately capture acoustic modes between the stator and rotor, the mesh density is adjusted to more than 100 points per wavelength of the principal T-S mode ($n=1, k=-1$).

FIGURE 2: COMPUTATIONAL DOMAIN FOR QUASI-3D URANS CALCULATION

FIGURE 3: SIMPLIFIED MODE SAHPES USED TO EVALUATE GENERALIZED MODAL FORCES (LEFT: FLAP MODE)

Total pressure, total temperature, and flow angle are specified at the inlet boundary, while static pressure is specified at the outlet boundary. Since the calculation is quasi-3D, a slip wall condition is applied at the spanwise ends, and a no-slip adiabatic wall condition is applied to the blade surfaces. The wall y^+ values are adjusted to around 3 on the no-slip walls, and wall functions are not used.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Evaluation of excitation forces

The present paper focuses on the excitation forces acting on the 1RB and 2RB blades caused by disturbances from the 1SV. Modal forces for the simplified flap mode, as shown in Figure 3, are used to evaluate these excitation forces. The simplified flap mode is described as parallel motion in the direction normal to the chord line of the blade, with a displacement of unity. In this study, blade size varies with the blade count; therefore, modal forces are normalized by the blade chord length to eliminate the effect of blade size. The normalized modal force was calculated by using following equation.

$$f_{norm} = \frac{f}{C} \quad (5)$$

3.2. Excitation forces without multi-stage interactions

To clarify the multi-stage effects, modal forces in the single-stage configuration will be discussed first. Figure 4 shows the modal forces on 1RB and 2RB, calculated using the single-stage configurations of 1RB-1SV and 1SV-2RB, respectively with constant rotational speed. In the Figure 4, the vertical axes represent normalized modal forces, while the horizontal axes represent the blade count of the rotor rows. Modal forces vary significantly with blade count in both 1RB and 2RB. The excitation force on 1RB increases around $B_1 = 20$, and the excitation force on 2RB increases around $B_2 = 16$. These changes of modal forces are closely related to the propagation characteristics (cut-on or cut-off) of the T-S modes. These trends have already been described in previous studies [4-6]; therefore, the detailed mechanism will not be presented in this paper. It is

(a) 1RB

(b) 2RB

FIGURE 4: NORORMALIZED MODAL FORCE FOR SIMPLIFIED FLAP MODE AT THE 1ST HARMONIC OF THE VANE PASSING FREQUENCY

known that unsteady pressure disturbances rapidly increase around the cut-on/off boundary, which is determined by flow characteristics and circumferential wave number. In the current configurations, the T-S mode of the disturbance from 1SV with 1RB ($B_1 - V_1$) becomes cut-on when $B_1 > 26$, and the T-S mode of the disturbance from 1SV with 2RB ($-V_1 + B_2$) become cut-on when $B_2 > 27$. These results are consistent with previous studies.

Figure 5 shows the amplitude of T-S modes corresponding to disturbances from the 1SV. The vertical axis represents the amplitude of the T-S modes, while the horizontal axis represents the blade counts. In this study, T-S modes were evaluated by performing a spatial Fourier transform on the unsteady pressure at the first harmonic of the vane passing frequency in the circumferential direction.

The amplitude of the T-S mode increases at $B_1 = 25$ upstream of 1SV and at $B_2 = 24$ downstream of 1SV. This result is consistent with previous studies [4-6]. In the downstream rotor, the strongest modal force is observed at $B_2 = 17$, whereas the strongest T-S mode is observed at $B_2 = 25$.

(a) 1RB

(b) 2RB

FIGURE 5: AMPLITUDE OF THE T-S MODE OF THE T-S MODE OF 1SV DISTURBANCE WITH ROTOR

This indicates that the modal force is not directly proportional to the amplitude of the T-S mode. This is because the modal force is determined by the product of the unsteady pressure disturbance and the mode shape, and depends on the relationship between the phase of the pressure disturbance and the direction of the modal vector.

As mentioned earlier, multi-stage interaction is caused by T-S modes generated in different stages; therefore, it is supposed that changes in the amplitude of the T-S mode may affect the excitation forces in other stages. This will be discussed in the following sections.

3.3. Excitation forces with multi-stage interactions

The effect of the blade count of 1RB and 2RB on excitation forces is presented in this section. Figure 6 shows the modal forces acting on the rotor rows. Figure 6(a) illustrates the changes in modal forces with varying 2RB blade counts while the 1RB blade count is kept constant ($B_1 = 16$). Conversely, Figure 6(b) shows the modal forces with varying 1RB blade counts while the 2RB blade count is kept constant ($B_2 = 17$). For reference, modal forces without multi-stage effects are also shown in Figure 6. Modal forces acting on each blade are

uniform when there is no adjacent rotor row. On the other hand, when an adjacent rotor row exists, the modal forces on each blade vary from blade to blade. This variation is caused by T-S modes generated in the adjacent stage, as previously mentioned in Reference [8].

The periodicity of blade-to-blade variation on the rotor differs depending on the blade count of the other rotor row, because the circumferential wave number of T-S modes from the other rotor row depends on its blade count. In these cases, a lower blade count leads to higher spatial variation, since the vane count of 1SV ($V_1 = 38$) is greater than that of the rotors. This trend is common for both the upstream and downstream stages, suggesting that the type of excitation source (i.e., potential or wake passing) is not related to the occurrence of multi-stage interaction.

(a) Modal Force on 1RB
($B_1 = 16$, $B_2 = \text{none}, 17, 21, 25, 29, 31$)

(b) Modal forces on 2RB
($B_1 = \text{none}, 16, 20, 24, 28, 30$, $B_2 = 17$)

FIGURE 6: NORMALIZED MODAL FORCES ACTING ON THE 1RB AT THE 1ST HARMONIC OF THE VANE PASSING FREQUENCY

As a result of multi-stage interaction, the maximum and average modal force also increases with the blade count of the other rotor row. However, the extent of this increase depends greatly on the blade count of the adjacent rotor. Figure 7 shows the relationship between the blade counts of each rotor and the magnitude of the maximum and average modal forces in the rotor blades. The horizontal and vertical axes represent the blade counts of 1RB and 2RB, respectively. The size of each bubble represents the magnitude of the modal force, with larger bubbles indicating higher modal forces. As mentioned previously, modal forces from conventional rotor-stator interaction and multi-stage interaction are affected by the propagation condition of the T-S mode, i.e., cut-on or cut-off. Therefore, the cut-off boundaries for each upstream and downstream stage are shown as dashed lines in the figure. In both cases, the maximum and average modal forces change drastically depending on the combination of 1RB and 2RB blade counts.

FIGURE 7: RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN COMBINATION OF BLADE COUNTS AND NORMALIZED MODAL FORCES FOR FLAP MODE ACTING ON 1RB AND 2RB AT THE 1ST HARMONIC OF THE VANE PASSING FREQUENCY (BUBBLE DIAMETER INDICATES NORMALIZED MODAL FORCES)

TABLE 2: BLADE COUNT CONFIGURATIONS

	B_1	V_1	B_2
Case A	20	38	21
Case B	20	38	25
Case C	28	38	21
Case D	28	38	25

In Figure 7(a), the maximum and average magnitudes of modal forces tend to be small in the region where B_1 is high and B_2 is low, corresponding to the case where the T-S mode is cut-on in the upstream stage and cut-off in the downstream stage. On the other hand, the magnitude of the modal force is relatively large in the region where both B_1 and B_2 are high, corresponding to the case where the T-S mode is cut-on in the downstream stage. This trend suggests that T-S modes from the downstream stage increase the magnitude of the modal force in the upstream stage. When considering changes in modal force with constant B_1 , the highest modal force is observed at $B_2 = 25$, which is the configuration where the T-S mode from the downstream stage becomes strongest, as shown in Figure 5. These tendencies are also observed for the downstream stage, shown in Figure 7(b), with the roles of 1RB and 2RB switched.

From a practical design perspective, the following important insights were obtained from these results. First, both the maximum and average modal forces depend on the blade counts of both rotor rows. Second, the configuration that increases the modal force is common to both 1RB and 2RB. These findings suggest that the excitation force can potentially be reduced by selecting an appropriate combination of blade counts.

3.4. Relationship between multi-stage interactions and T-S modes

In this section, the relationship between modal forces arising from multi-stage interaction and T-S modes is investigated. To simplify the discussion, four configurations listed in Table 2 are considered. Case B is the configuration in which the modal force magnitude is the largest, whereas Case C is the configuration in which the modal force magnitude is quite small. Cases A and D are selected to examine the effect of changes in the blade count of the other rotor row.

Modal forces acting on the rotor blades can be decomposed into modal forces for individual nodal diameters. Figures 8(a) and 8(b) show the decomposed modal forces on 1RB and 2RB, respectively, for Cases A to D listed in Table 2. The vertical axis represents the modal force decomposed for each nodal diameter. These modal forces are obtained by applying a discrete Fourier transform to the complex modal forces of each blade in the rotor row. The horizontal axis represents the nodal diameter; however, the corresponding scatter indices n_1 and n_2 are shown instead of the nodal diameter for clarity. In these figures, $n_i = 0$ indicates the nodal diameter corresponding to the 1SV disturbance, and other n_i values indicate scattered components.

(a) 1RB

(b) 2RB

FIGURE 8: DECOMPOSED MODAL FORCES FOR FLAP MODE ACTING ON 1RB AND 2RB AT THE 1ST HARMONIC OF THE VANE PASSING FREQUENCY

In Figure 8(a), modal forces of the scatter index $n_2 = 1$ in Case B and D are significantly higher than those of the other components, and they are larger than the modal force of $n_2 = 0$, which is caused by the disturbance of 1SV passing. This result indicates that excitation due to T-S modes from the downstream stage may have an impact of the same order as conventional rotor-stator interaction. Additionally, the modal forces of $n_2 = 0$ vary with the 2RB blade count even when the 1RB blade count remains the same (as seen in the comparison between Cases A and B, and Cases C and D). In this study, the 1RB and 2RB blade counts were selected as even and odd numbers, respectively, to distinguish the circumferential wave numbers of T-S modes from each stage. Therefore, T-S modes from the downstream stage do not coincide with the nodal diameter of excitation due to rotor-stator interaction in the upstream stage. The results suggest that the changes in modal forces of $n_2 = 0$ are caused by not only the acoustical superposition of through T-S modes.

FIGURE 9: DISTRIBUTION OF THE AMPLITUDE OF PRESSURE FLUCTUATION AT THE 1ST HARMONIC OF THE VANE PASSING FREQUENCY

In Figure 8(b), the phenomenon is essentially the same as that observed in Figure 8(a). Changes in the modal force of $n_1 = 0$ are also observed in the downstream stage, even though the modal forces at $n_i = 0$ should be identical to those shown in Figure 5 if multi-stage interaction is absent.

The amplitude of pressure fluctuations at the first harmonic of the vane passing frequency is shown in Figure 9. According to the figure, the amplitude varies in the circumferential direction, which is caused by multi-stage interaction. The spatial period of this variation depends on the blade count configuration, as shown in Figure 6. The pressure amplitude level differs among Cases A to D, with large pressure fluctuations observed in Cases B and D ($B_2 = 25$ for both). These differences are directly related to the variation in excitation force shown in Figure 7.

T-S modes resulting from rotor-stator interaction are shown in Figure 10. The vertical axis represents the amplitude of the T-S mode for each circumferential wave number component. The horizontal axis represents the scatter indices, which are the integer values defined in Equation (2). Only T-S modes with $k_1 = -1$, corresponding to disturbances from 1SV and their scattered components, are shown in these figures.

The T-S mode of $(n_1, k_1, n_2) = (0, -1, 0)$ in Figure 10 represents the circumferential pressure profile of the 1SV potential, and it does not vary with blade count configurations, since the 1SV vane count and flow conditions were not changed in this study. On the other hand, the modal forces for $k_1 = -1$ shown in Figure 8 do change with blade count configuration. This result indicates that the 2RB blade count affects the scattering of the T-S mode with 1RB. As mentioned earlier, in

(a) Upstream 1SV (Inter Stage of 1RB-1SV)

(b) Downstream 1SV (Inter Stage of 1SV-2RB)

FIGURE 10: AMPLITUDE OF TS MODES AT INTERSTAGE OF UPSTREAM AND DOWNSTREAM 1SV

the blade count configurations investigated, the circumferential wavenumbers of the T-S modes in the upstream and downstream 1SV do not match, so this phenomenon cannot be explained by the simple superposition of T-S modes. Therefore, further research is required to understand how the T-S mode from another stage affects.

Focusing on the T-S modes from the other stage, it is found that the amplitude of these T-S modes is comparable to, or even higher than, the amplitude of T-S modes generated by direct rotor-stator interaction. Furthermore, although some of these modes are cut-off in the adjacent stage, a high amplitude is still observed in the corresponding stage. These results suggest that selecting the blade count to achieve a cut-off condition for the T-S mode, to prevent its influence on other stages, may sometimes be ineffective. Where the conditions close to the cut-on boundary, the pressure disturbance becomes stronger and the

axial damping rate decreases. Therefore, even in cut-off conditions, the T-S mode may not decay sufficiently and could reach adjacent stages. However, it should be noted that this study was conducted using a simplified quasi-3D model. In configurations closer to the actual geometry, the decay of the T-S mode may show different tendencies from those observed in the quasi-3D model.

4. CONCLUSION

The relationship between blade count selection and forcing due to rotor-stator interaction was investigated numerically. URANS calculations with various blade count combinations were conducted to calculate the forcing. To evaluate the strength of the forcing, modal forces for the simplified flap mode were calculated. Modal forces in each configuration were analyzed, and the following findings were obtained.

- Excitation forces due to vane passing disturbances depend on the blade count combination of the upstream and downstream stages, not only on the blade count of the rotor itself.
- Excitation forces tend to be large when the blade count configuration results in an increased modal force and the T-S mode from the downstream or upstream stage is strong. In this configuration, the T-S modes in both stages are positioned just before the cut-on boundary.
- Excitation forces are suppressed when the excitation force in the stage is low and the T-S mode from the other stage is sufficiently cut-off.

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